

STUDY ON INTERFACE COMPATIBILITY OF CARBON FIBER/EPOXY RESIN COMPOSITE BY SINGLE FIBER FRAGMENTATION TEST

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1 Introduction

Carbon fiber is a kind of new-style material with a series of excellent performances, such as high tenacity, high modulus, heat-resistance, corrosion resistance and so on [1, 2]. As a kind of reinforcing fiber of advanced material, carbon fiber and its composite are widely used in aerospace, weapon manufacture, national defense, building trade, automobile parts and many other fields, and the composites' interfacial properties have been the hot topics in related studies. The interface of composite plays a major part in transferring stress between reinforcement and resin matrix. Interfacial properties directly influence the overall properties of the composites [3, 4]. With the development of high performance T-series carbon fiber, T700, T800 will gradually replace T300 to become a new generation of universal carbon fiber for their better performance. Interface compatibility and interfacial bonding properties of fiber and resin have a major impact on the mechanical properties and applications of the composites.

As one of the important factors to determine mechanical performance, IFSS measurement requires special micromechanical techniques as follows: single fiber fragmentation test [5, 6], single fiber micro-droplet test [7, 8] and micro-indentation test [9, 10] etc. Compared with macro-study on the interface, micromechanical tests have been developed with the advantage of intuition and convenience. One of the most important micromechanical tests, Single Fiber Fragmentation Test (SFFT), is focused on in this paper, because single fiber fragmentation test has become a widely used method for fiber strength and adhesion characterization under conditions closely approximate to those encountered in a real composite material [11-13]. So the study on interfacial compatibility of high performance carbon fibers reinforced composite has important practical significance.

In this paper, the interfacial characterization by Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), Atomic force microscopy (AFM) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectrum (XPS) of two kinds of carbon fiber (AF and BF) were carried out. Single fiber tensile test (SFST) was used to measure single fiber strength. By using the single fiber fragmentation test, micro-interface property of AF/E-43 epoxy resin, BF/E-43 epoxy resin and BF/LY-1 epoxy resin composites were investigated to reveal the relationship between surface characteristics and composites' interfacial properties, and to supply steps to the matching of carbon fiber/epoxy resin composites.

2 Experimental Method

2.1 Materials

The epoxy resin E-43 and LY-1 used in this paper were supplied by Dong Nan Chemical Research Institute, polyacrylonitrile based carbon fibers (AF and BF) in the experiment were commercially provided. In order to discuss the influence of sizing on the surface appearance or the composite interface, the sizing agent on carbon fiber surface was extracted with Soxhlet Extractor [14]. The carbon fiber desizing treatment was performed in acetone in 80°C for 12 hour, and then the fiber was dried in 70°C in the oven.

2.2 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) test

The SEM images of carbon fibers were characterized by a ZEISS SUPRA 55VP field emission scanning electronic microscopy.

2.3 Atomic force microscopy (AFM) test

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements were performed with a Veeco D3000 instrument manufactured by VEECO Corporation. A single carbon fiber was fastened to a steel sample mount with double sided tape. All images were collected in air using the tapping mode with a silicon nitride probe. Roughness analysis was carried out from the images obtained over a 3 μm×3 μm area.

2.4 X-ray Photoelectron Spectrum (XPS) test

The carbon fibers were analyzed using a Thermo VG ESCALAB250 X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (XPS). The spectra were collected using a Mg Ka X-ray source (1253.6 eV) with a power of 300 W.

2.5 Single fiber fragmentation (SFF) test

For evaluation of the composite interface, SFF test was conducted. SFF specimen consists of a single fiber embedded in a resin matrix with dog-bone shape which was shown as Fig. 1.

As specimen is loaded in tension, the fiber will be loaded through an interfacial shear stress transfer mechanism (shear-lag) [15]. The axial fiber stress increases from zero at the ends and assumes constant stress over its length. At a certain level of applied load, the fiber will fracture. If the loading is continued, the shear-lag mechanism will transfer load into the broken fiber and repetition of the failure process will occur until the remaining fiber fragments are so short that the shear stress transfer becomes insufficient to cause any further break [16]. This state is called break saturation, and the final fiber fragmentation length is referred to as the critical length L_c . A stronger bond between fiber and matrix enables more transfer of load into the fiber which results in a shorter critical fragment length [17].

With the help of light microscope, the process in fragmentation test from stress loading to the break saturation was observed. When the specimen was loaded, the region around a fiber break exhibited a colored pattern between crossed polarizers, called birefringence [18]. This phenomenon was caused by shear stresses in the matrix [19]. It was found that the distance of the adjacent break points would equally distribute between $1/2 L_c$ and L_c . As a result,

$$L_c = \frac{4}{3} \bar{L} \quad (1)$$

Which \bar{L} is the average fragment length, it satisfies the Weibull distribution:

$$P = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x-\gamma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right] \quad (2)$$

The Eq. (2) can be changed into the equation:

$$\ln[-\ln(1 - P_i)] = \alpha \ln(L_i - \gamma) - \alpha \ln \beta \quad (3)$$

Which α , β , γ are fixed parameters, and the probability is P_i as the fiber break length is L_i ,

$$P_i = \frac{i-0.5}{n} \quad (i=1,2,\dots,n).$$

The distances of adjacent break points were measured as L_i , the fixed parameters were gained after the fitting according to the Eq. (3). The average fragment length was calculated by the equation below:

$$\bar{L} = E(L_i) = \gamma + \beta \Gamma(1 + 1/\alpha) \quad (4)$$

Finally, the interface shear stress was calculated based on Kelly-Tyson equation [20]:

$$\tau = \frac{d_f \sigma_f}{2L_c} \quad (5)$$

Which d_f is the fiber diameter, σ_f is the fiber strength. L_c is the critical fragment length, τ is the interface shear stress.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 The surface topography

The SEM and AFM images of carbon fibers are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. The surface topography of AF studied appears to consist of grooves along the fiber axial direction; BF is opposite to the AF. SEM and AFM images consistently reveal that the sizing changes the surface topography on a microscopic scale. The sizing increases fiber surface smoothness. Increasing the fibers surface roughness could enhance the mechanical interlocking. Therefore, the smooth surface of the samples after sizing has negative effect on mechanical interlocking.

Calculated by the software NanoScope Analysis, the results of the roughness analysis of sizing and desizing fibers are shown in Table 1. The results indicate that the surface roughness value (Ra) of the sizing and desizing AF are 41.3nm and 53.3nm, respectively, which is much higher than the sizing and desizing BF. The AFM images of sizing carbon fibers show a slight decrease in roughness compared to the desizing carbon fibers. The Ra for the sizing AF and BF decreased slightly from 53.3 nm to 41.3 nm and from 16.7 nm to 12.4 nm, respectively, which means the desizing enhances the roughness of the fiber's surface.

3.2 The chemical characteristics of surface

The surface composition of sizing and desizing carbon fibers was determined by XPS and the results are shown in Table 2. Values of the binding energy (BE) and the atomic concentration (AC) are listed for each photopeak. The sizing and desizing fiber surface is composed of carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, sulfur and silicon. Carbon and oxygen are the most abundant elements at the surface. Other elements

may be present, but only at atomic concentrations no more than 5%. Besides, the O/C rate of the sizing and desizing AF and the sizing and desizing BF present as 25%, 34% and 18%, 30%, respectively. Oxygen atoms on the carbon fiber presents active atom, it will improve the chemical activity of the carbon fiber, and make a great contribution to chemical bonding between carbon fiber and resin matrix [21, 22]. As the O/C rate of desizing carbon fiber presents higher, it can be concluded that desizing improves the chemical activity of the fiber's surface.

Fig.4 shows typical XPS C1s fitting curve spectra for sizing and desizing carbon fibers. The percentages of functional groups (C-OH or C-OR; C=O; COOH or COOR) on sizing and desizing carbon fibers were estimated from these fitting curves of C1s photopeaks and are listed in Table 3. Values of the binding energy (BE) and the percent contribution (PC) of each curve fitting photopeak to the total C1s photopeak are summarized in Table 3.

The functional groups C-OH or C-OR and C=O were detected on all sizing and desizing carbon fibers, but the functional group COOH or a strongest bond COOR was only detected on the desizing BF. The percentage of functional groups containing oxygen decreased for sizing carbon fibers when compared to the desizing carbon fiber, because the carbon fiber had obtained surface treatment to increase amount of surface active functional groups containing oxygen before sizing in the carbon fiber production line. The covered sizing layer with less active functional groups containing oxygen on the carbon fibers will decrease numbers of the surface active sites. It is reasonable that the decreased functional groups containing oxygen on sizing carbon fibers are disadvantage to the fiber/matrix adhesion. It has been suggested that the surface treatment has more pronounced effect on improving the interfacial strength than the sizing in References [23-25].

3.3 Interfacial shear stress (IFSS) of the carbon fiber

The IFSS results are shown in Table 4. The IFSS of sizing carbon fibers show a slight decrease compared to desizing carbon fibers. The IFSS for the sizing AF/E-43, sizing BF/E-43 and BF/LY-1 decreased slightly from 102.55MPa to 91.97 MPa, from 49.84MPa to 49.18MPa and from 45.92 MPa to 28.35 MPa, respectively. The results indicate that desizing fiber has a stronger bond with the resin

matrix, and also indicate that desizing AF has a strongest bond with the E-43 resin matrix.

The interaction of interface between carbon fiber and matrix consists mainly of physical effects and chemical bonding. It is generally believed that the mechanical engagement is the most important physical effects in the interface. According to the results of SEM and AFM, desizing enhances the roughness of fiber surface, which benefits the mechanical engagement between fiber and resin. In the meanwhile, based on the results of XPS, desizing improves the chemical activity of fiber surface. With higher O/C rate, resin more easily reacts with active functional groups on desizing fiber surface to form chemical bonding. As are of greater physical and chemical bonding, desizing fiber has a stronger bond with the resin matrix, monofilament composite has higher IFSS. Therefore, all the results indicate that the desizing fibers have good interface compatibility with the resin compared to sizing fibers, and the desizing AF/E-43 has the strongest bond and best interface compatibility.

The sizing for carbon fiber could serve a lubricant to prevent fiber damage during subsequent textile processing such as weaving and prepreg processing, while being compatible with the matrix resin and not obviously decreasing the fiber/matrix interface adhesion.

3.4 Birefringence in the single fiber fragmentation test

With strong interfacial bond, the fiber embedded in the sample breaks while tensile stress increases. If bonding of interface is strong enough to transfer stress, plastic deformation will occur in the matrix around fiber breakpoints. As a result, the matrix has different refractive index, and show a sharp X-type birefringence under the polarizing microscope. The birefringence images in the fragmentation test were shown as Fig. 5.

A strong interface to transfer stress breakpoints surrounding matrix have different degrees of plastic deformation, resulting in a different refractive index, showing a sharp X-type birefringence under the polarizing microscope, as shown in Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b). When the interfacial adhesion is not strong enough, the energy released when the fiber breakage is difficult to cause the destruction of the matrix, but transferred to the interface along the fiber axis, causing the adjacent interface debonding. In Fig. 5(e), the birefringences of BF/LY-1 monofilament composite are not in X-type but elongated along the fiber, and the distances of adjacent breakpoints are

longer, which indicates the debonding in the interface between BF and LY-1 resin.

4 Results

The results of this study revealed the relationship between surface characteristics and composites' interfacial properties, and the following conclusions are made.

- (1) The surface topography of AF studied appears to consist of grooves along the fiber axial direction; BF is opposite to the AF. According to AFM results, surface roughness value of both sizing and desizing AF are much higher than BF. Sizing fibers show a slight decrease in roughness compared to the desizing carbon fibers.
- (2) The O/C rate of the sizing and desizing AF and BF present as 25%, 34% and 18%, 30%, respectively. Desizing improves the chemical activity of the fiber's surface. The percentage of functional groups containing oxygen decreased for sizing carbon fibers when compared to the desizing carbon fibers.
- (3) The IFSS for the sizing AF/E-43, sizing BF/E-43 and BF/LY-1 decreased slightly from 102.55MPa to 91.97 MPa, from 49.84MPa to 49.18MPa and from 45.92 MPa to 28.35 MPa, respectively. As a result, desizing fiber has a stronger bond with the resin matrix, and the desizing AF/E-43 has the strongest bond and best interface compatibility.
- (4) In the single fiber fragmentation test, the samples of AF/E-43 show sharp X-type birefringence. However, for the BF/LY-1, the birefringence is elongated, and the distances of adjacent breakpoints are longer.

5 References

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Fig.1 The sample of SFF

(c)

(d)

Fig.2 SEM images of carbon fibers surface.

(a) Sizing AF; (b) Desizing AF; (c) Sizing BF (d) Desizing BF

(a)

(b)

Fig.3. AFM images of carbon fibers surface.
 (a) Sizing AF; (b) Desizing AF; (c) Sizing BF (d) Desizing BF

Table 1 The roughness of carbon fiber surface

fiber	Ra(nm)
Sizing AF	41.3
Desizing AF	53.3
Sizing BF	12.4
Desizing BF	16.7

Fig.4. Curve fitting C1s photoelectron peaks of carbon fibers.
 (a) Sizing AF; (b) Desizing AF; (c) Sizing BF (d) Desizing BF

Table 2 Surface chemical analysis of XPS results

fiber	C 1s		O 1s		N 1s		S 2p		Si 2p		O/C
	B.E. (eV)	A.C. (%)									
Sizing AF	285.0	74.73	532.7	19.03	400.2	3.03	168.5	0.85	102.3	2.36	0.25
Desizing AF	285.0	69.36	532.9	23.39	400.6	3.28	169.5	0.74	102.4	3.23	0.34
Sizing BF	284.8	83.76	532.8	14.70	400.1	0.63	-	-	102.2	0.69	0.18
Desizing BF	284.8	74.44	533.0	21.90	401.1	0.52	-	-	102.4	3.14	0.30

Tab 3 XPS C1s curve fitting results of sizing and desizing carbon fibers

fiber	-C-C- or -C-H-		-C-OH or -C-OR		-C=O		-COOH or -COOR	
	B.E. (eV)	P.C. (%)	B.E. (eV)	P.C. (%)	B.E. (eV)	P.C. (%)	B.E. (eV)	P.C. (%)
Sizing AF	285.0	62.12	286.5	20.10	287.0	17.78	—	—

Desizing AF	285.0	57.94	286.5	30.05	287.3	12.01	—	—
Sizing BF	284.8	70.84	286.4	23.23	287.3	10.93	-	-
Desizing BF	284.8	53.71	286.5	37.53	287.8	6.85	290.4	1.91

Table 4 The IFSS results in SFF test

fiber/resin	IFSS(MPa)
Sizing AF/E-43	91.97
Desizing AF/E-43	102.55
Sizing BF/E-43	49.18
Desizing BF/E-43	49.84
Sizing BF/LY-1	28.35
Desizing BF/LY-1	45.92

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig. 5 Birefringence images in the fragmentation test(magnification: 50)

- (a) Sizing AF/E-43; (b) Desizing AF/E-43; (c) Sizing BF/E-43;
(d) Desizing BF/E-43; (e) Sizing BF/LY-1; (f) Desizing BF/LY-1